

MODERN METHODS OF PREVENTING IRON DEFICIENCY IN WOMEN AND CHILDREN

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Rational nutrition, high intake of iron inhibitors, chronic blood loss, vomiting disorders, chronic diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, as well as the classification of the World Health Organization should be taken into account when doctors diagnose anemia. According to the WHO classification, the hemoglobin level is 110 g / l in pregnant women, 120 g / l in women, 110 g / l in children under 5 years of age, 115 g / l in children aged 5-12 years, 120 g / l after 12 years of age, and 130 g / l in men. forms. It is recommended to use the hemoglobin cyanide method in the determination of hemoglobin, which is a modern and reliable method.

Although a significant reduction in maternal and child mortality has been achieved in our country, in some cases, ECGs are still a direct cause of maternal mortality or lead to serious complications during childbirth. Anemia is one of these diseases. This is due, firstly, to the fact that it is widespread among women of childbearing age and pregnant women in the country (among all ECGs, it is 60-70% in some regions), and secondly, it adversely affects the birth process and causes various serious complications. This disease causes various complications during childbirth in 47.3% of cases. These figures are 90% in Karakalpakstan, 74.8% in Bukhara, 72.1% in Tashkent and 60.7% in Fergana. In particular, the dynamics of children with anemia in Tashkent region can be seen in the table below (Table 1). The analysis of childhood diseases was studied based on statistical data.

In 2018, anemia in Tashkent region has the following indicators, including 7.3% in China, 4.2% in Bostan, 11% in Boka, 28.6% in Parkent, 15% in Lower Chirchik, 61.3% in Zangiota, 37% in Bekabad, 37% in Piskent. 12.8%, Upper Chirchik 12.6%, Angren 18.6%, Bekabad 21.3%, Middle Chirchik 22.7, Chirchik 22.7%, Akhangaran 12.6%, Yangiyul 3.7%, Almalyk 35.9%, Akkurgan 23.2%, Kibray 55.0%.

The study of the epidemiology of anemia and the application of advanced modern methods of its primary, secondary and tertiary prevention in practice based on the results is a topical issue.

Among children aged 0-14 in 2020, this figure will increase from 7.3% to 17% in Chinaz district, from 4.2% to 7.9% in Bostanlyk, from 11% to 18.9% in Buka, and from 28.6% in Parkent. 13.7%, in Lower Chirchik district from 15% to 11.2%, Zangiota from 61.3% to 59.3%, Bekabad from 37% to 35.4%, in Piskent from 12.8% to 17.5% , In Upper Chirchik from 12.6% to 11.9%, Angren from 18.6% to 25.8%, Bekabad from 21.3% to 25.4%, in Middle Chirchik from 69.7% to 65.7% in Chirchik city from 22.7% to 59.3%, in Akhangaran district from 12.6% to 12.9%, in Yangiyul from 3.7% to 10.4%, in Almalyk district from 35.9% to 34.5%. % ga. In Akkurgan it can be seen from 23.2% to 21.4%, and in Qibray district from 55.0% to 53.6%.

It should be noted that the anemia rate was found to be slightly higher in Angren, Middle Chirchik, Chirchik and Zangiota districts than in other districts.

Given that pediatric morbidity was mainly due to primary morbidity, we analyzed the overall morbidity.

In 2019-2020, the incidence of diseases among children aged 0-14 years decreased, (33.8%).

The decrease in the incidence of childhood diseases was due to the decrease in both acute and chronic diseases. The decrease in morbidity in children was mainly due to the following classes of diseases: circulatory system diseases (63%), skin and subcutaneous klechatki diseases (52%), respiratory diseases (44.3%), nervous system diseases (42 , 7%), ear and mammary tumor diseases (40.7%), infectious diseases (31.5%), endocrine system diseases (30.3%), congenital anomalies (18.1%). Among the nosologies of the above class of diseases can be seen a decrease in diseases such as myopia (na 22.1%), viral hepatitis B (na 88.1%), bronchial asthma (20.4%).

An increase in childhood illnesses (38.2%) due to injuries, traumas, external causes of illness calls parents, UAS, to awareness.

The increase in anemia among children (by 8.2%) is due to poor quality of children's nutrition, unregulated diet, excessive consumption of artificial mixtures.

Enriching foods with iron-containing products is the most effective and inexpensive method. The results of this program will be felt in a few years. The amount of iron in iron-fortified foods covers only the physiological needs of the body.

Obstetricians and gynecologists should intensify contraceptive measures until women of childbearing age with TTK fully recover and are discharged from the dispensary.

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